

DESK REVIEW OF JOB SATISFACTION COMPONENTS & EMPLOYEE RETENTION IN COMMERCIAL BANKS IN KENYA

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Abstract

Employees are the life-blood of any organization. Even though most of the organizations are nowadays are found to be technology driven, but still human resources are required to run the technology. They are the most vital and dynamic resources of any organization and they should be motivated. With all round development in each and every area of the economy, there is stiff competition in the market. With this development and competition, there are lots of avenues and opportunities available in the hands of the human resources. The biggest challenge that organizations are facing today is not only managing these resources but also retaining them. Securing and retaining skilled employees plays an important role for any organization, because employees' knowledge and skills are central to companies' ability to be economically competitive. Employee remuneration is one of the most important variables in determining whether or not an employee stays with an organization. The purpose of this study will be to establish the influence of remuneration on employee retention in Commercial Banks in Kenya. Good remuneration program motivates employees in an organization. Adequate reward system in the organization would reduce the employee turnover rate.

Key Words: job satisfaction, Employee Retention, Commercial Banks, Remuneration

1.1 Background to the Study

Retention of employees entails developing strategies to motivate employees to stay within the company (Chen, 2014). It refers to effort made by organizations to retain talented employees in their workforce. This is because a company's ability to succeed is determined by its ability to retain employees (Hilmer & McRobert, 2014). High employee turnover decreases

productivity and increases cost of recruitment, induction and training of placement employees. Hence, human resource practitioners in organizations are developing sound employee retention strategies, such as ensuring job satisfaction among its employees (Balamurugan & Abinaya, 2016).

Job satisfaction is defined as a worker's feelings about their work or the attitude towards work and it is affected by the perception of a person (Parvin & Kabir, 2017). According to Azeez (2017) job satisfaction shows the alignment level between work expectations and benefits that are derived from the work. As the business environment changes, so is job satisfaction and hence the need to review employee satisfaction factors from time to time.

1.1.1 Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is defined as the extent to which one's physiological, psychological, and environmental states all come together to allow one to carry out one's duties well. Happiness in the workplace is largely an internal state of mind. The answer to this question varies widely from one worker to the next. Essentially, it represents the intangible factors that inspire people to get their work done (Vroom, V. H. 1995).

It is a multifaceted phenomenon impacted by elements like communication, work environment, pay and promotion, loyalty and autonomy (Jalagat, 2016). Employee job satisfaction is largely regarded as a "win-win" approach for both companies and their staff. According to Azeez (2017), satisfaction improves attitude, which is essential in determining specific training requirements. It also promotes high productivity, decreased absenteeism, decreased sick leave, saves on recruitment and retention related costs, reduction in workers stress and enhanced employee loyalty.

A report from Central Florida affirmed that self-fulfillment and workplace conditions, predicts hourly employee retention globally. Employees who are positive in regard to working-hours experience, job fulfilment, and high job satisfaction level are also highly likely to remain with their present employer. Additionally, having a fun working environment and flexible hours is a top motivator for employee retention (Wildes, 2017). In the Middle East region, Clavin

(2017) notes that, enhanced service opportunities, better working conditions and professionalism are some reasons for mobility in employment other than pay increment which is viewed as the aim of leaving present jobs. In Turkey many firms have adopted feedback, training, career growth programs and communication which are growing in spite the present demanding global economic situations. This provides a strong strategy to assist firms in the region in employee's retention (Sangaran & Jeetesh, 2015).

1.1.2 Employee Retention

According to Siggler (2013), employee retention refers to organization's ability to retain its employees which can be represented by a simple statistic. Leighn (2012), defines employee retention as keeping those employees that keep the organizations in business. Abraham (2010), it is important that the organization hires the right employee and strives to safeguard them to avoid losing them. It's the duty of organizations to focus on reducing employee turnover with an aim of decreasing recruitment cost, training costs, accidents of new employee are often higher, wastage is often higher with new employees, avoiding time wastage as a resource, and loss of talent and organizational knowledge.

Depending on each employee, job satisfaction can be thought of as an affirmative or negative assessment of his or her work experience (Cronley & Kim, 2017). From a psychological point of view, job satisfaction refers to how content workers are with the various parts and responsibilities of their jobs (Suifan, Diab, and Abdallah, 2017). Since job happiness is linked to positive business outcomes including increased productivity, happier customers, and a more committed workforce, it has received much attention (Lu, Lu, Gursoy, and Neale, 2016).

How satisfied a person is with their job depends on what they receive from the business and how they evaluate its value to them (Ramalho et al., 2018). Previous studies have shown that an increase in job satisfaction leads to a greater likelihood of employee retention. Evidently, happy workers have a beneficial effect on their outlook and productivity on the job (Ramalho et al., 2018; Suifan et al., 2017). Employees' positive emotions and their rational understanding of the corporate setting are inextricably linked thanks to the role played by positive attitudes (Huang, Chen, Liu, and Zhou, 2017). There is a strong positive correlation between job

satisfaction and employee retention, which makes job satisfaction an important indicator of a positive work environment, according to a study conducted by Tnay et al. (2013) among employees of an Australian pathology company.

1.1.3 Commercial Banks

In Kenya, the banking industry is governed by, the Central Bank of Kenya Act, the Banking Act, the Companies Act and prudential guidelines provided by the CBK. The responsibility of CBK is to formulate and implement monetary policies, foster solvency, liquidity and a proper operating financial system. At the end of year 2020, commercial banks were 41, mortgage financial company 1, microfinance banks 14, representative offices of foreign banks 9, money remittance providers 19, foreign exchange bureaus 69 and 3 credit reference bureaus. The banks have formed the Kenya Bankers Association (KBA), which acts as a lobbying group for the banking sector's interests. The KBA provides a forum for members to discuss issues that affect them (CBK, 2020).

1.2 Statement of the Problem:

The banking industry has been facing increased competition from fintechs which are not licensed by the CBK and therefore have greater flexibility in the business that they conduct. This implies that there is also high competition in retaining talented employees (PWC, 2020). Statistics in Kenya show that about 54 percent of employees are likely to leave their present employment in six months' time while 35 percent are not sure (Jalagat, 2016). Employees are main assets of any firm and the role they play cannot be undermined. Increased employee retention lowers or completely eliminates the expense of recruiting, hiring, and training new employees. So, it is crucial to create suitable internal organizational structures and procedures that will guarantee staff retention (Madueke, 2017).

At a time when the banking sector is pressured to grow and have diverse workforce, the organizations may view satisfaction of employees as a burden. Also, one of the best indicators of a pleasant workplace is job satisfaction. A contented worker is more productive, more dedicated to their work, and more likely to stick to the company for the long run. Hence, employers in the banking sector must put employee happiness first by making sure they are

aware of their needs, provide a desirable working environment, respect their personal goals, enhancing supervision quality and foster working relationships (Kwakye, 2018).

Previous scholars have studied the concept of job satisfaction. For instance, Silaban and Margaretha (2021) examined the relationship between work-life balance and job satisfaction and employee retention and revealed an association of work-life balance and employee retention. Alemwa (2014) researched on the Development Bank of Ethiopia to determine the association between work happiness and employee job performance and found that job satisfaction had a significant positive effect on satisfaction. In Lagos State, Nigeria, Bello (2021) researched on the effect of job satisfaction on employees' intention to leave the sector and found that there was no correlation between the payment system and the propensity for employee turnover.

Gebregziabher, Berhanie, and Berihu (2020) conducted a research on the association between nurses' intention to leave their jobs and job satisfaction at the Axum comprehensive and specialized hospital in Tigray, Ethiopia. Mule (2020) focused on the connection between professional growth and staff retention in the county government of Meru and found that career development has a significant relationship with employee retention. On the other hand, Yalabik, Rayton and Rapti (2017) on facets of job satisfaction and work engagement sought to determine the effect of operating conditions, rewards, supervisor, nature of work, coworkers and communication, pay, benefits and promotion on work engagement within commercial banks in Kenya. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The target population for this study comprised of 42 commercial banks operating in Kenya and the unit of analysis were head of human resource manager. The study adopted the census technique. Primary data was collected by use of questionnaires. Quantitative data was collected and analysed using descriptive statistics such as mean score, standard deviation was used Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Regression model was used to determine the relationship between independent variables and dependent. The study established that enhancement of work environment, leadership have positive a significant influence on work engagement within commercial banks in Kenya. This study recommends that HR managers in banks should come

up with strategic measures that further seek to enhance work environment and that organizational leaders need to adopt best guidance values qualities.

However, it is established that there is limited literature to conclude on the relationship existing between job satisfaction and staff retention in Kenya. Most of the existing studies were conducted in other countries such as United States, China, Ethiopia and Nigeria. Others were conducted on other sectors such as public sector. The few studies on banks were case studies conducted in one bank only. However, the current study considers all commercial banks in Kenya. Existing studies were also noted to have utilized inadequate research models. Variables in the study were also operationalized differently. The study thus identifies that there exist empirical, methodological, conceptual and contextual gaps. The aim of the current study is to establish the impact of job satisfaction on employee retention in the banking sector in Kenya.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The general objective is to establish the influence of job satisfaction components on employee retention in the commercial Banks in Kenya.

1.2.1 Specific objectives

- i. To establish the effect of training on employee retention in commercial banks in Kenya.
- ii. To determine the effect of communication on employee retention in commercial banks in Kenya
- iii. To find out the effect of promotion on employee retention in commercial banks in Kenya
- iv. To establish the effect of career growth programs on employee retention in commercial banks in Kenya.

2.0 Theoretical Literature

The study will be guided by the expectancy and social exchange theories that relate to job satisfaction and employee retention.

2.1 Expectancy Theory

Vroom (1964) developed the theory. It is a theory of motivation, and it states that valence, expectancy, and instrumentality all have an effect on an employee's motivation. Expectancy is a term used to describe what workers anticipate from carrying out their tasks and is connected to exceptional performance and results. By identifying elements that encourage workers to give their best effort, such as a training program, retention may be assured. Furthermore, it is essential that they have the resources, knowledge, and backing of the managers and supervisors. Instrumentality is the idea that achieving success will result in a reward. A company can do this by following through on promises of additional benefits such as bonuses or promotions. Employees must believe that their efforts will be rewarded if they perform well. Transparency in the employee-rewarding process is a critical requirement for instrumentality.

Employees' valence is how much they value any reward associated with their efforts. As a result, it is critical for a company to identify individual values and personal needs of employees as sources of motivation. One employee may place a high value on money, whereas another may place a high value on vacation days (Vroom, 1964). However, the theory has been criticized for appearing idealistic because few people believe in a strong link between rewards and performance. Furthermore, the theory's application is limited because, in the majority of firms, reward is not always directly related to performance. It is also related to factors such as position, responsibility, effort, or education (Banjoko, 2002). The theory shows that employee's satisfaction is key in ensuring their retention.

2.1.1 Social Exchange Theory

Malinowski's anthropological works provided the basis for social exchange theory. Blaus (1964) popularized it by distinguishing between economic and social exchange and he is thus credited as the founder of the social exchange theory. Social exchange theory explains a set of human interactions based on estimates of rewards and punishments. This theory states that interactions are determined by the rewards or punishments that are expected from others, which are evaluated using a cost-benefit analysis model. The theory was initially developed to examine people's social behaviour in terms of resource exchange.

Employees' sense of obligation at work, according to Eisenberger, Armeli, Rexwinkel, Lynch, and Rhoades (2001), is important since it persuades them to compensate for favourable treatment gotten from their company. Perceived organizational support relates to the extent that workers believe the organization values their contributions. Workplace justice is seen as establishing the conditions for employee participation. Increased levels of justice perception, according to Cropanzano and Mitchell (2005), are linked with employees who perform effectively and making contributions to organizational success. Workers who engage in organizational activities like volunteering are more likely to stay with the company.

2.2 Empirical Literature

Silaban and Margaretha (2021) conducted a study targeting millennial employees in Bandung City, Indonesia to examine the relationship between work-life balance and job satisfaction and employee retention. The purpose of the research was to explore the effect of work-life balance on job satisfaction and employee retention of the millennial generation employees in the city of Bandung, Indonesia. The sample used in this study was 196 employees from various fields of work. Analysis of data used simple linear regression, by testing the quality of the data through validity and reliability test. Study results found that there was an effect of work-life balance on job satisfaction as much as 8.3%, and there was an effect of work-life balance on employee retention of 4.4%. The findings revealed an association of work-life balance and employee retention. Additionally, the research had important implications for leadership in the company, such as providing a good work environment, supporting facilities to provide morale for employees, practicing fair compensation and salary without giving excessive burden to and building good communication between employees and leaders. The recommendation from this research concluded that, work-life balance was not a new concept in human resource research; therefore, this topic will always be examined in many studies.

Chaturvedi and Sangwan (2016) researched on job satisfaction and its impact on employee retention in Genpact, one of the leading Business Processing Outsourcing (BPO) industries in Jaipur. A structured questionnaire was the tool for collecting data. The study was based on the factors that affect an employee's job satisfaction which were measured through a structured questionnaire. A sample size of 100 middle level staff in Jaipur's BPO firms were administered

with the questionnaires. The hypothesis of the study covered employees' views on career development, compensation and reward, relationship with supervisors and colleagues, communication and motivation and work environment in the organization. The study used the 5-Likert-scale technique to analyze the questionnaires. Results indicated that employees were not satisfied with the career opportunities offered by the organization, training opportunities were not offered, there was less employee involvement in decision making and the organization does not provide a conducive work environment. The researcher concluded that, job satisfaction affects employee retention and if not well offered it can lead to high employee turnover. Focusing on employee satisfaction can positively impact the organization as it increases employee productivity, performance, quality of work, profits, commitment to the organization and reduces turnover and absenteeism. In BPO, employees were not satisfied with all the components related with the job satisfaction and therefore it was suggested that the organization should curb the rate of attrition by coming up with innovative strategies to retain employees.

In Pakistan, Inayat (2021) conducted research on job satisfaction and its impact on employees' performance in Peshawar private sector organizations. One hundred and eighty employees from Peshawar-based private companies were chosen as a sample. The study's instruments included a self-made Performance Evaluation Form (PRF) and a Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ-short form). The type of occupation had a significant

correlation with job satisfaction. Similarly, it was confirmed that job satisfaction positively correlated with employee performance.

In Lagos State, Nigeria, Bello (2021) conducted research on the effect of job satisfaction on employees' intention to leave at the Lagos State hotel industry. The study adopted a survey research design. The research population comprised of employees of four- and three-stars registered hotels in Ikeja, Lagos State Nigeria (Hotels in Ikeja, 2019). It had the land mass of 356,861 hectares and 25 million populations. Ikeja is known for highest concentration of hotels and other forms of lodging facilities put at 65% of total room stock in Nigeria (JLL, 2018). The total registered hotels in Ikeja Lagos State were put at 923 out of which 60 of the hotels were selected through a systematic sampling technique since it was practically impossible for the researchers to sample the entire staff in each of the 60 selected hotels in Ikeja hence, Taro Yamane. Partially least squares structural equation modelling was used for the analysis and structured questionnaires were used to collect the data. The study found a statistically significant correlation between job stress, promotion potential, supervisor support, and workplace culture and employees' intention to leave. Aside from that, there was no correlation between the payment system and the propensity for employee turnover. The study also recommended that managers and operators of hotel businesses in Lagos state should give more attention to issue of staff promotion. Thus, staff should be offered satisfactory chances of being promoted, and appreciable speed of promotion should be maintained.

In Ethiopia, Gebregziabher, Berhanie, and Berihu (2020) research on the association between nurses' intention to leave their jobs and job satisfaction at the Axum comprehensive and specialized hospital in Tigray, Ethiopia. A total of 148 nurses were included in the study using a systematic random sampling technique. The study was conducted from January 2018 to June, 2019. The Data were collected using semi-structured self-administered questionnaires and a cross-sectional study design was used. Semi-structured questionnaires were used to gather the data. Bivariate logistic regression analysis was used. The results demonstrated a significant relationship between overall intention and job satisfaction. The research was conducted using institution based cross-sectional study design. Out of 148 nurses, more than half (64.9%) had the intention to leave the organization. The finding of the study showed that the level of job

satisfaction was significantly associated with the overall intention. Nurses who were unsatisfied on their job autonomy were 2.55 (95% CI: 1.194, 5.466) more likely to intend to leave their workplace than nurses who reported to be satisfied.

On the other hand, Yalabik, Rayton and Rapti (2017) on facets of job satisfaction and work engagement sought to determine the effect of operating conditions, rewards, supervisor, nature of work, co-workers and communication, pay, benefits and promotion on work engagement within commercial banks in Kenya. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The target population for this study comprised of 42 commercial banks operating in Kenya and the unit of analysis were head of human resource managers. The study adopted the census technique. Primary data was collected by use of questionnaires. Quantitative data was collected and analysed using descriptive statistics such as mean score, standard deviation was used Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Regression model was used to determine the relationship between independent variables and dependent. The study established that enhancement of work environment, leadership have positive a significant influence on work engagement within commercial banks in Kenya.

3.0 Methodology

The study adopted empirical review where journals and published reports from reputable sources enabled the analysis of the study variables where 13 journals were reviewed for the employee retention while 5 materials enable the analysis of job satisfaction variable. The study also analysed two theories; social exchange and expectancy theories in relation to the study variables. Different reviews at the international, regional and local level were considered in the study where 8 articles were obtained from credible sources to provide empirical reviews. From these sources, the methodology adopted were descriptive, crosssectional, survey, census and quantitative research design with different target populations; millennial generation, middle level management and all cadres of employees. There were studies that adopted Taro Yamane to identify sample size with the application of systematic random sampling. Majority of the studies adopted semi-structured questionnaire with the incorporation of 5-point Likert scale, validity and reliability was checked with analysis performed using simple linear and multiple

linear regression and partially least square equation structural modelling with the aid of SPSS. Presentation was in form of mean, standard deviation, frequency distribution tables and graphs.

4.0 Findings and Conclusions

From the empirical reviews, on the exploration of work-life balance on job satisfaction and employee retention, the study found that there is an association of work-life balance and employee retention. On the objective of job satisfaction and its impact on employee retention, it was found that employees were not satisfied with their career opportunities that were being provided by their organizations. The study also established that there were no training opportunities as well as less involvement of staff. The study revealed that on job satisfaction and employee performance in Peshawar, there was a significant relationship with occupation and job satisfaction. The study objective of job satisfaction and employee intention to leave established that there was a statistical significance between job stress, potential promotion, work place culture, supervisor support and employee intention to leave. It was found that there was no connection between payment system and intention to leave. On the association of nurse's intention to leave and job satisfaction indicated that there was a significant relationship between overall intention to leave and job satisfaction. On the study's objective on job satisfaction and work engagement, the findings established that there is an enhancement of work environment where leadership have a positive and significant influence on job engagement.

5.0 Recommendations

The study recommends organizations to provide good working environment and supporting of employees for enhanced retention. The study also makes recommendations that the management should incorporate good human resource practices that will reduce staff intention to leave thereby save on recruitment and hiring costs associated with new hires. The study makes recommendations that the management should give more attention to staff promotion to enable employees achieve their potential especially employees with distinguished experience and skills. This will enhance their satisfaction and reduce attrition rate. The study makes recommendations that there should be more training opportunities where all staff with identified skill gaps should be able to attend. This will enhance their satisfaction and

productivity at work hence improve their retention. Recommendation is made that there should be more support from supervisors that will motivate staff to perform better at their work place. Supervisor support should also have feedback to employees for improvement that will lead to more job satisfaction hence reduced attrition. This study consisted of empirical review. The study recommends that future study should be primary data collection to validate the findings.

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